

D.5.3

Seed bank and plant covers report.

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Executive summary

Report D5.3, the first deliverable for task T5.4 “Seed Bank and Plant Covers” within work package WP5 “Soil Biodiversity,” presents an assessment of the soil seed bank and groundcover vegetation in selected olive groves across the Mediterranean, as part of the Soil O-live project. This deliverable collects standardized information on landscape and vegetation composition to ensure compatibility and interoperability across Soil O-live work packages, supporting the adoption and utilization of project solutions by the market. The Hellenic Agricultural Organization DEMETER (ELGO), as a member of the Soil O-live consortium, contributed to WP5 by providing expertise and data on soil biodiversity in olive agroecosystems.

A total of 52 olive orchards in Spain, Italy, Morocco, Greece, and Portugal were monitored, including 21 under traditional management, 11 under high-density intensive management, and 19 under organic management. Traditional systems varied in tree spacing and trunk number, while high-density systems involved mechanized, intensive cultivation with heavy soil tillage and chemical inputs. Organic orchards emphasized soil conservation and biological preservation without the use of chemical products.

In each orchard, five monitoring stations per hectare were paired with existing LUCAS soil sampling points. Groundcover vegetation and floristic composition were assessed in 1 × 1 m subplots, surveyed repeatedly across seasons to capture species with differing phenology. Soil seed banks were sampled using 20 cm cores, separated by depth and location (beneath trees vs. open streets), and germinated in greenhouse conditions for taxonomic identification.

Results indicated that organic orchards consistently supported higher species richness and greater herbaceous cover, while high-density orchards exhibited lower values. Patterns of herbaceous cover closely mirrored seed bank diversity, highlighting the link between aboveground vegetation and potential soil seed reservoirs. Less intensive management, lower planting density, and greater habitat heterogeneity favored more diverse and balanced plant communities, whereas dominance patterns (q_2) remained stable across management types.

At the regional scale, Spain and Greece showed higher species richness and cover, whereas Morocco displayed lower diversity, with only ground cover and species presence data available, precluding inclusion in hills number analyses. Diversity was positively correlated with older orchards, fertile and well-structured soils, and spatially complex landscapes. These findings underscore the importance of promoting practices that enhance structural heterogeneity, soil quality, and low-intensity management to conserve and support biodiversity in Mediterranean olive agroecosystems.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Summary and scope

The purpose of Report D5.3 is to provide information on the soil seed bank and groundcover vegetation composition in selected olive groves under different management systems within the Soil O-live project. This report aims to provide baseline information on the taxonomic diversity of these groups in relation to key soil health drivers. This information will be subsequently used to support the implementation of effective soil amendments and restoration practices.

1.2. Project presentation overview

Soil O-LIVE aims to:

- Conduct a comprehensive diagnosis of soil status in terms of contamination, degradation, and functional condition across different management regimes and spatial scales.
- Investigate the relationship between soil health status and olive oil production and quality.
- Implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices that promote measurable improvements in soil biodiversity and functionality, leading to enhanced olive oil quality and safety.
- Define robust ecological thresholds to support the development of clear standards and regulations for a novel certification scheme for healthy soils in European olive orchards.

1.3. Brief introduction about groundcover vegetation and seedbank

Conventionally, plant cover in olive orchards consists of native vegetation that emerges spontaneously during autumn and winter. This ground cover is composed of species adapted to anthropogenically disturbed environments and characterized by high reproductive capacity.

The plant community mainly consists of annual or short-lived species, with about two-thirds being broadleaved (dicotyledonous) plants. The rest consists mostly of grasses, sedges, and to a lesser degree, ferns. Most ground cover species are angiosperms (see Table 1) and primarily reproduce by seed. However, many also propagate vegetatively through structures like rhizomes, tubers, taproots, bulbils, or stolons.

Several species possess fruit or seed traits that facilitate short- and long-distance dispersal via wind, water, agricultural machinery, or animals. In perennial plants, roots and other vegetative organs are generally vigorous and contain substantial reserve resources, enabling persistence under environmental stress and repeated soil disturbance associated with orchard management practices.

Under Mediterranean conditions, winter annual weeds typically germinate in autumn or early winter, flower in spring, and complete seed production by late spring or early summer of the following year.

Table 1. Most common ground flora families (Holm, 1978).

Family	Number of species
Poaceae	44
Cyperaceae	12
Asteraceae	32
Polygonaceae	8
Amaranthaceae	7
Brassicaceae	7
Leguminosae	6
Convolvulaceae	5
Euphorbiaceae	5
Chenopodiaceae	4
Malvaceae	4
Solanaceae	4

Ground vegetation changes continually. In addition to the seasonal cycle, the small-scale pattern of species changes from year to year as individuals grow, spread, decay and die. Variations in soil moisture content due to periods of heavy rain or drought generate perpetual adjustments in the balance between species. Superimposed on these changes are responses to changes in the structure and composition of the stand, both natural and due to management.

Some of the characteristics of the groundcover flora are i) rapid seedling growth and the ability to reproduce when young; ii) quick maturation or short time in vegetative stage; iii) environmental plasticity, which means the ability to grow under a wide range of climatic and edaphic conditions; iv) production of seeds able to resist decay for long periods in soil and remain dormant v) the ability to mature much more seeds than agricultural plants (e.g. *Chenopodium album* L. can mature till 200.000 seeds) and vi) competitive ability for nutrients, light, and water that can be accomplished also by special means (e.g., rosette formation, climbing, allelopathy); and vii) resistance to management and environmental stress.

Ground cover can be also consisted by invasive species. An example in Eastern Europe are the olive growers that in order to avoid such unwanted influence, they maintain a winter ground cover of *Oxalis pes-caprae* (Oxalidaceae), because of its smothering capacity against other weeds. As a result, *O. pes-caprae* has dominated the olive herbaceous flora in some areas and excluded other indigenous species (Petsikos et al., 2007).

Ground cover flora is usually eliminated in traditional cultivation systems in late March or early April, before it starts competing for water and it is then usually disrupted, mainly by mechanical mowing and/or herbicides. In irrigated orchards competition occurs when groundcover vegetation consumes water intended for crops while causing water loss by seepage via root channels and transpiration. In addition, vegetative ground cover harbors a wide range of organisms thereby increasing their opportunities to persist in the environment and reinfest crops in succeeding years. In Mediterranean olive orchards tillage is practiced for the reduction of the risk of fire, though tillage can worsen the problem favoring perennial plants. In general, weed management systems that rely on single control techniques stabilize weed populations and encourage emergence of weeds that are not affected by the control technique.

Though, ground cover maintenance is one of the most important strategies in tree crop systems and is widely used around the world. Compared to tillage management, ground cover has multiple functions to improve the environmental performance of tree crop systems, including:

- (1) improving soil physical structure (Garcia et al., 2018), along with nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) retention and enrichment (Wei et al., 2017, Zhong et al., 2018);
- (2) elevating soil organic carbon and land productivity (Novara et al., 2019);
- (3) enhancing soil microbial diversity and enzyme activity, thus increasing soil nutrient cycling (Vukicevich et al., 2016, Zheng et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2020);
- (4) improving fruit tree yield and quality (Xiloyannis et al., 2011, Li et al., 2019).
- (5) significantly reducing soil loss, runoff and nutrient loss in tree crops (Alvarez et al., 2017, Garcia et al., 2018, Martinez-Mena et al., 2020).

In addition to their soil-improving functions, ground cover plants may play an important role in integrated pest management in orchards. A diverse plant community can influence arthropod natural enemy populations by providing critical food or habitat resources that might not be found in a simpler ecosystem (Perrin, 1980; Andow, 1991; Bugg & Waddington, 1994).

Annual weeds reproduce and disperse as seeds. Soil can maintain seeds from a broad range of plant species, which are through time accumulated in its profile, creating weed seed banks in various habitats. Substantial amounts of seeds are comprised in the soil seed bank in different states; viable, non-dormant and dormant. Thus, it consists of both new weed seeds recently shed, and older seeds that have persisted in the soil from previous years. Dormant seeds can be reserved in the soil profile for many years to germinate when conditions become favorable (Warr et al. 1993) so not all germinate in one flush, but over a longer period. Seed dormancy allows viable weed seeds to survive tillage or herbicide application and then germinate later when conditions are safe, so the seedbank reflects the “memory” of recent weed management practices in the field and will determine future weed infestations. That is why seedbanks have the potential to restock the weed population on a field. Agricultural soils can contain hundreds of weed seeds per square meter, but seed banks can range from 0 to as much as 1 million seeds per square meter (Menalled, 2013).

Soil seed banks are therefore important in understanding vegetation history as the vegetation composition in terms of plant species. At the same time seed banks act as the determinant of future vegetation, especially after a disturbance (Warr et al. 1993); information peculiarly important in restoration projects, where preferred species have been lost from the vegetation but survive in soil. This two-faced vision of past and future weed composition qualifies

the seed bank as an important key element to understanding population dynamics, and thus contribute in the establishment of appropriate weed management programs (Ambrosio et al., 2004), forecasting of weed infestations (Ball and Miller, 1989; Creech et al., 2008). Since alternative weed management is consistently ranked at or near the top of IPM priority lists, knowledge of the density and composition of weed seeds in the soil is important and may be helpful for crop rotation planning (Wiles and Schweizer 2002). Although weed maps based on above ground observation of weeds are potentially useful, especially for perennial species, weed seed bank estimates provide a much more complete indicator of past and future problems with annual weed species. Seed bank composition is always under a dynamic change (figure 1) and is affected by environmental and biological factors, management practices and the local vegetation, since a small percentage weed seeds are those that entered from outside the field. Seasonal and environmental factors interact to influence weed seed germination pattern in the seed bank.

Edapho-climatic conditions affect some seeds and can lead either to death or dormancy if germination does not occur quickly; in response to these conditions some species like dandelion resort to strategies, such as the production of non-dormant seeds that can germinate quickly. Decline in weed seed bank may occur by a range of factors such as germination, seed predation (Van Mourik et al., 2005), seed decay to death (Gal landt, 2006) and deep seed burial to layers from where emergence onto the soil surface is impossible (Honda, 2008). In addition, the seed bank composition is influenced by seed dispersal and seed longevity as well (Sumberová & Ducháček 2017). Many weed seeds have special attachments that allow them to be dispersed by wind, water or animals. Seeds can also enter a field by dispersal, from sources such as mud on equipment, as a contaminant in crop seed, animals and manure. Since weed seeds disperse both horizontally and vertically in the soil profile, understanding vertical distribution of seeds is important because it can help us predict weed emergence patterns.

In arable fields, management practices such as tillage, crop rotation, and weed control affect seed germination. For example, pre-irrigation and preplant tillage can be considered as cultural practices in the management of the soil seedbank that deplete the upper soil layer of nondormant weed seeds and can result in as much as 50% weed control. Crop rotation is also effective for weed management, since changing patterns of disturbance can diversify selection pressure. This diversification prevents the emergence of weed species adjusted to the practices associated with a single crop. Crop sequences employ varying patterns of resource competition, related to allelopathic interference, soil disturbance, and variable weed management strategies. So, otherwise well-adapted weed species show reduced in a more diverse environment (Buhler 1997).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Participating Olive orchards

A total of fifty-two olive orchards were monitored around the Mediterranean in Spain, Italy, Morocco, Greece, and Portugal, of which 21 belong to a traditional management system, 11 to an intensive and 19 to an Organic (Table 2). Traditional cultivation encompasses different planting densities (between 5 and 12 meters spacing among trees) and can have 1 to 3 tree trunks. High-density olive groves include mostly mechanized cultivation with tree densities exceeding two hundred trees per hectare, and super intensive cultivation surpassing 1000 trees per hectare. Both traditional and intensive cultivation systems involve excessive soil tillage with heavy machinery, as well as the systemic application of herbicides and pesticides. Organic olive groves are based on the premise of total soil conservation and the preservation of biological resources without the use of chemical products.

Table 2. Orchard records structured by countries and cultivation methods

SPAIN		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD2	ES-ORG4
ES-TD5	ES-HD3	ES-ORG6
ES-TD7	ES-HD8	ES-ORG11
ES-TD9	ES-HD22	ES-ORG12
ES-TD15	ES-HD40	ES-ORG13
		ES-ORG14
MOROCCO		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
MR-TD24	MR-HD25	MR-ORG23
MR-TD26		
MR-TD27		
MR-TD28		
MR-TD29		
GREECE		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
GR-TD30	GR-HD43	GR-ORG32
GR-TD31	GR-TD44	GR-ORG33
GR-TD35		GR-ORG34
GR-TD36		GR-ORG38
GR-TD37		GR-ORG39
GR-TD46		GR-ORG45
		GR-ORG47

2.1 Groundcovers sampling and inventory

An ecological evaluation is usually an essential component of any site management plan, as this identifies, or confirms the features of interest, that are present and assesses their overall importance. This assessment forms the basis for setting the overall objectives for the site and conservation objectives for each feature, which can be considered one of the most important functions of the management planning process.

2.1.1 Sampling units

In each of the studied olive grove plots, five monitoring stations per hectare were established for the assessment of ground cover and seed bank composition. The differentiation of sampling locations is important, as plant species may be more easily detected in certain habitats than in others. Vegetation sampling points were selected to spatially coincide with previously established LUCAS soil sampling points within each plot, so that each of the five monitoring stations was directly paired with a LUCAS soil sampling location, ensuring comparability between soil and vegetation data. At each station, a one square meter (1×1 m) (Fig. 3) subplot was delineated for the evaluation of ground cover and floristic composition. The same sampling stations were surveyed repeatedly across different seasons in order to identify the maximum possible number of species, accounting for differences in phenology and the optimal periods for species identification.

Figure 3. Different types of quadrats.

2.1.2 Abundance and soil cover %

To measure abundance of the vegetative soil cover we counted the number of plants present and what area of ground they cover. This provides a quantitative measure, usually requiring fewer locations to be visited.

2.1.3 Inventory.

Differences in frequency distribution curves, especially the level of skewness, can be used to inform the feasibility and effectiveness of future monitoring programs. In each of the experimental orchards, individuals of each plant morphotype encountered were collected to allow subsequent identification. The samples were described as found and later identified by the collectors and specialists at the University of Jaén using flora books and floristic identification keys. As a methodological approach, the samples were systematized based on species, year, and collection site.

Figure 4. Samples of preserved biological material.

2.1.4 Seed bank sampling and inventory.

The composition of the seed bank was analyzed by sampling a 20 cm soil core, distinguishing between areas located beneath trees and those in open street sites. In the greenhouse, the soil cores were separated into two depth intervals (0–10 cm and 10–20 cm), and the seeds present in the soil were germinated for taxonomic identification.

Figure 5. Example of soil core extraction for seed bank.

Figure 6. Photographs of the seedling identification phase.

2.1.5 Data analyses

The data analysis was performed using the statistical software R. The vegan package was used to calculate Hill's numbers and biodiversity indices. To examine the relationships between soil properties and these indices, other libraries such as corrplot and FactoMineR were used.

4. Results and discussions.

4.1. Groundcovers.

Table 3. Herbaceous species of seed bank by orchard.

Olive grove code	Species
ES HD2	<i>Capsella bursapastoris</i> , <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Calendula arvensis</i> , <i>Sinapis alba</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Urospermum picroides</i> , <i>Rubia peregrina</i> , <i>Galium murale</i> , <i>Fedia cornucopiae</i> , <i>Nonea vesicaria</i> , <i>Crepis vesicaria</i> , <i>Urtica urens</i> , <i>Diploaxis virgata</i> , <i>Sonchus asper</i> , <i>Lysimachia foemina</i> , <i>Scabiosa triandra</i> , <i>Sysimbrium orientale</i> , <i>Leontodon longistrostris</i> , <i>Chondrilla juncea</i>
ES HD3	<i>Arenaria ES</i> , <i>Echium plantagineum</i> , <i>Diploaxis virgata</i> , <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Helianthemum ES</i> , <i>Lactuca serraiola</i> , <i>Leontodon longistrostris</i> , <i>Lysimachia foemina</i> , <i>Herniaria hirsuta</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , <i>Cyperaceae ES sp1</i> , <i>Anacyclus clavatus</i>
ES HD8	<i>Astragalus hamosus</i> , <i>Calendula arvensis</i> , <i>Erodium malacoides</i> , <i>Erodium moschatum</i> , <i>Geranium rotundifolium</i> , <i>Bromus hordeaceus</i> , <i>Lolium rigidum</i> , <i>Crepis foetida</i> , <i>Lamium amplexicaule</i> , <i>Medicago orbicularis</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Allium ES</i> , <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Hordeum marinum</i> , <i>Medicago polymorpha</i> , <i>Ornithogalum narbonense</i> , <i>Urtica urens</i> , <i>Capsella bursapastoris</i> , <i>Diploaxis virgata</i> , <i>Lysimachia foemina</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Malva sylvestris</i> , <i>Crepis vesicaria</i> , <i>Trifolium tomentosum</i>

ES HD22	<i>Calendula arvensis, Erodium malacoides, Lysimachia foemina, Althaea hirsuta, Muscari neglectum, Diplotaxis virgata, Anacyclus clavatus, Catapodium rigidum, Filago pyramidata, Pulicaria paludosa, Rostraria cristata, Bromus rubens, Trifolium tomentosum, Hordeum marinum, Medicago minima, Astragalus hamosus, Fylago pyramidata, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus madritensis, Geranium dissectum, Medicago polymorpha, Scorpiurus mericatus, Trifolium scabrum, Urospermum picroides, Leontodon longistrostris, Trifolium campestre, Festuca ambigua, Centaurea melitensis, Galium murale</i>
ES HD40	<i>Calendula arvensis, Erodium malacoides, Lysimachia foemina, Althaea longiflora, Echium plantagineum, Sinapis alba, Medicago polymorpha, Anacyclus clavatus, Torilis nodosa, Leontodon longistrostris, Rubia peregrina, Lolium rigidum, Plantago lagopus, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus rubens, Carduus nigrescens, Convolvulus arvensis, Hordeum marinum</i>
PT HD51	<i>Coleostephus myconis, Convolvulus arvensis, Lolium rigidum, Malva multiflora, Medicago polymorpha, Bromus diandrus, Rumex pulcher, Sonchus oleraceus, Torilis nodosa, Crepis vesicaria, Geranium dissectum, Hordeum marinum, Vicia sativa, Bromus rubens, Galium parisiense, Bromus hordeaceus</i>
PT HD52	<i>Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus rubens, Daucus carota, Ammi majus, Echium plantagineum, Galium aparine, Lolium rigidum, Lysimachia foemina, Cladanthus mixtus, Plantago lagopus, Silene gallica, Trifolium campestre, Crepis vesicaria, Erigeron PT, Mentha ES, Raphanus raphanistrum, Urospermum picroides, Avena sterilis, Erodium moschatum, Hordeum marinum, Lamarckia aurea, Malva trimestris, Medicago polymorpha, Medicago trunculata, Hirschfeldia incana, Trifolium resupinatum, Bromus madritensis, Phalaris canariensis</i>
PT HD53	<i>Crepis vesicaria, Galium aparine, Hordeum marinum, Cladanthus mixtus, Plantago lagopus, Raphanus raphanistrum, Trifolium resupinatum, Urospermum picroides, Astragalus hamosus, Bromus hordeaceus, Lolium rigidum, Lysimachia foemina, Lythrum hyssopifolia, Poa trivialis, Bromus rubens, Erodium moschatum, Polygonum PT, Medicago polymorpha, Phalaris canariensis</i>
MR HD25	<i>Malva parviflora, Hordeum marinum, Sorghum halepense, Calendula arvensis, Brassica nigra, Convolvulus altheoides, Echium plantagineum, Elytrigia repens, Papaver rhoeas, Anagallis foemina</i>
ES ORG4	<i>Anacyclus clavatus, Calendula arvensis, Capsella bursapastoris, Diplotaxis virgata, Erodium malacoides, Erodium moschatum, Filago pyramidata, Fumaria officinalis, Lysimachia foemina, Medicago polymorpha, Nonea vesicaria, Plantago lagopus, Astragalus hamosus, Avena sterilis, Bromus rubens, Crepis vesicaria, Erodium ciconium, Medicago orbicularis, Papaver roeas, Torilis nodosa, Anthemis arvensis, Euphorbia exigua, Silybum marianum, Leontodon longistrostris, Malva sylvestris, Eruca sativa, Muscari neglectum, Scorpiurus mericatus, Veronica polita, Heliotropium europaeum, Lamium amplexicaule, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus madritensis, Hordeum marinum, Medicago minima, Hirschfeldia incana, Fylago pyramidata, Convolvulus altheoides, Echium plantagineum, Lolium rigidum, Medicago trunculata, Roemeria argemone</i>
ES ORG6	<i>Torilis nodosa, Sonchus asper, Silybum marianum, Brachypodium distachyon, Euphorbia exigua, Lysimachia foemina, Plantago lagopus, Sinapis alba, Centaurea melitensis, Bromus rubens, Medicago polymorpha, Crepis vesicaria, Moricandia arvensis, Filago pyramidata, Astragalus hamosus, Diplotaxis virgata, Anacyclus clavatus, Lolium rigidum</i>
ES ORG11	<i>Torilis nodosa, Capsella bursapastoris, Silene colorata, Erodium malacoides, Erodium moschatum, Phalaris canariensis, Malva sylvestris, Anacyclus clavatus, Diplotaxis virgata, Veronica polita, Calendula arvensis, Lamium amplexicaule, Lysimachia foemina, Malva hispanica, Nonea vesicaria, Valeriana cornucopiae, Medicago orbicularis, Hedypnois rhagadioloides, Carduus tenuiflorus, Medicago polymorpha, Euphorbia exigua, Romeria argemone, Bromus rubens, Sonchus oleraceus, Stachys germanica, Lamium amplexicaule, Rostraria cristata, Hordeum marinum,</i>

	<i>Ornithogalum narbonense, Papaver rhoeas, Bromus hordeaceus, Trifolium tomentosum</i>
ES ORG12	<i>Astragalus hamosus, Rostraria cristata, Crepis vesicaria, Anthemis arvensis, Medicago polymorpha, Medicago minima, Muscari neglectum, Scorpiurus mericatus, Salvia verbenaca, Avena sterilis, Bromus rubens, Calendula arvensis, Leontodon longistrostris, Erodium malacoides, Filago pyramidata, Galium aparine, Hordeum marinum, Lolium rigidum, Ornithogalum narbonense, Plantago lagopus, Sonchus oleraceus, Euphorbia exigua, Geranium rotundifolium, Medicago orbicularis, Valeriana cornucopiae, Diplotaxis virgata, Rhagadiolus stellatus, Urospermum picroides, Erodium moschatum, Catapodium rigidum, Festuca ambigua, Linum tenuifolium, Trifolium tomentosum, Lysimachia foemina, Papaver rhoeas, Silene colorata</i>
ES ORG13	<i>Allium ES, Brachypodium distachyon, Calendula arvensis, Bupleurum lancifolium, Filago pyramidata, Anacyclus clavatus, Lysimachia foemina, Althaea longiflora, Geranium rotundifolium, Muscari neglectum, Cichorium intybus, Asparagus acutifolius, Bromus rubens, Coronilla scorpioides, Lolium rigidum, Medicago trunculata, Medicago orbicularis, Medicago polymorpha, Nigella damascena, Ornithogalum narbonense, Pellenia spinosa, Petroragia nanteuilii, Plantago lagopus, Hirschfeldia incana, Scorpiurus mericatus, Tripodium tetraphyllum, Crepis vesicaria, Erodium malacoides, Sonchus oleraceus, Veronica polita, Capsella bursapastoris, Diplotaxis virgata, Fylago pyramidata, Noccaea perfoliata, Torilis nodosa, Galium murale, Rubia peregrina, Lamium amplexicaule, Medicago minima, Bromus hordeaceus, Tolpis barbata, Convolvulus altheoides, Echinaria capitata, Leontodon longistrostris, Trifolium stellatum, Centaurea melitensis, Atractylis cancellata, Bromus madritensis, Cuscuta planiflora, Ononis pubescens, Trifolium strictum, Aegilops geniculata, Astragalus hamosus, Carduus tenuiflorus, Eryngium campestre, Triticum aestivum</i>
ES ORG14	<i>Torilis nodosa, Astragalus hamosus, Filago pyramidata, Galium aparine, Diplotaxis virgata, Lysimachia foemina, Medicago polymorpha, Plantago lagopus, Reseda ES, Sonchus oleraceus, Veronica polita, Anacyclus clavatus, Crepis foetida, Herniaria ES, Erodium moschatum, Echium plantagineum, Euphorbia exigua, Capsella bursapastoris, Rostraria cristata, Carduus tenuiflorus, Calendula arvensis, Trifolium tomentosum, Convolvulus arvensis, Papaver roheas, Silene colorata</i>
IT ORG17	<i>Avena fatua, Bromus sterilis, Calendula arvensis, Chamaemelum fuscatum, Convolvulus tricolor, Galacties tomentosus, Galium verrucosum, Hedysarum coronarium, Lulium multiflorum, Lysimachia arvensis, Medicago polymorpha, Oxalis pes-caprae, Picris hieracioides, Sonchus asper, Diplotaxis eruroides ssp. eruroides, Phalaris paradoxa</i>
IT ORG18	<i>Avena sterilis, Beta vulgaris ssp. maritima, Calendula arvensis, Chamaemelum fuscatum, Diplotaxis eruroides ssp. eruroides, Lulium multiflorum, Medicago polymorpha, Oxalis pes-caprae L., Soncuhs asper, Stellaria neglecta spp cupaniana, Convolvulus tricolor, Cynodon dactylon</i>
IT ORG19	<i>Avena fatua, Convolvulus tricolor, Diplotaxis eruroides ssp. eruroides, Erodium moschatum, Galacties tomentosus, Lulium multiflorum, Oxalis pes-caprae, Bromus rigidus, Calendula arvensis, Chrysanthemum coronarium, Emex spinosa, Medicago polymorpha, Soncuhs asper, Stellaria neglecta spp. cupaniana, Chenopodium ambrosioides, Cynodon dactylon, Malva multiflora, Oxalis pes-caprae</i>
GR ORG38	<i>Anthemis chia, Asphodelus ramosus, Avena sativa, Papaver rhoeas</i>
GR ORG39	<i>Anthemis chia, Avena sativa, Cistus creticus, Papaver rhoeas, Thymbra capitata</i>
PT ORG42	<i>Leontodon longistrostris, Filago pyramidata, Calendula arvensis, Capsella bursapastoris, Cerastium glomeratum, Festuca ambigua, Ornithopus compressus, Biserrula pelecinus, Parentucellia latifolia, Epsilonium PT, Lysimachia arvensis, Anthemis cotula, Trifolium tomentosum, Veronica polita, Lathyrus angulatus, Andryala integrifolia, Bromus storilis, Crepis vesicaria, Anthyllis lotoides, Galium aparine, Hordeum marinum, Plantago coronopus, Poa annua, Viola arvensis, Geranium</i>

	<i>dissectum, Medicago polymorpha, Silene gallica, Viola kitaibeliana, Bromus hordeaceus, Echium creticum, Ornithopus pinnatus, Jasione montana, Tolpis barbata</i>
IT ORG48	<i>Allium oleraceum, Asparagus acutifolius, Avena barbata, Bromus arvensis, Bromus catharticus, Centaurea jacea, Convolvulus arvensis, Dactylis glomerata, Daucus carota, Elymus pungens, Galium album, Galium aparine, Lolium perenne, Lotus corniculatus, Medicago orbicularis, Nigella damascena, Plantago lanceolata, Potentilla reptans, Ranunculus acris, Rubia peregrina, Sanguisorba minor, Sherardia arvensis, Trachynia distachya, Verbena officinalis, Vicia villosa, Bromus erectus, Calystegia sepium, Muscari neglectum, Allium roseum, Blackstonia perfoliata, Bromus madritensis, Crepis vesicaria, Galium caprarium, Geranium molle, Lathyrus sylvestris, Picris hieracioides, Quercus ilex, Rumex crispus, Trifolium pratense, Ulmus minor, Allium sphaerocephalon, Centaurium erythraea, Clinopodium nepeta nepeta, Hypochaeris achyrophorus, Scabiosa atropurpurea, Trifolium hirtum, Trifolium hybridum, Aegilops geniculata, Anacamptis pyramidalis, Himantoglossum hircinum, Linum strictum, Pallenis spinosa, Tordylium apulum, Trifolium angustifolium, Trifolium aureum, Urospermum dalechampii, Linaria vulgaris, Lindernia dubia, Trifolium campestre, Vicia tetrasperma, Asplenium onopteris, Ruscus aculeatus, Smilax aspera, Asparagus tenuifolius</i>
IT ORG49	<i>Agrostis stolonifera, Asparagus acutifolius, Asparagus tenuifolius, Astragalus monspessulanus, Avena barbata, Clinopodium nepeta nepeta, Convolvulus arvensis, Dactylis glomerata, Doricnium hirsutum, Foeniculum vulgare, Lathyrus sativus, Nigella damascena, Pallenis spinosa, Picris hieracioides, Plantago lanceolata, Reseda lutea, Scabiosa atropurpurea, Smilax aspera, Sonchus asper, Sulla coronaria, Torilis arvensis, Urospermum dalechampii, Verbascum sinuatum, Vicia dasycarpa, Vicia sativa, Calystegia sepium, Hedera helix, Rubia peregrina, Ruscus aculeatus, Aegilops geniculata, Centaurium erythraea, Crepis foetida, Gladiolus italicus, Helminthotheca echioides, Hordeum vulgare, Inula viscosa, Linum strictum, Linum usitatissimum, Reichardia picroides, Trifolium alexandrium, Trifolium angustifolium, Trifolium arvense, Trifolium hybridum, Verbena officinalis, Allium sphaerocephalon, Bromus madritensis, Catapodium rigidum, Helichrysum stoechas, Origanum vulgare, Phleum pratense, Trifolium hirtum, Alopecurus pratensis, Andryala integrifolia, Coronilla scorpioides, Cynodon dactylon, Lysimachia arvensis, Medicago sativa, Sanguisorba minor, Serapias parviflora, Silene gallica, Trachynia distachya, Briza maxima, Lathyrus sylvestris, Trifolium stellatum, Daucus carota, Malope malacoides, Phalaris paradoxa, Allium roseum, Bromus erectus, Carex flacca, Clematis vitalba, Rostraria cristata, Asplenium onopteris</i>
MR ORG23	<i>Emex Spinosa, Papaver rhoeas, Silybum marianum, Euphorbia biumellata, Evolvulus alsinoides, Glebionis coronaria, Bupleurum rotundifolium, Phalaris brachystachys, Malva trimestris, Calendula stellata, Hordeum murinum, Convolvulus althaeoides, Gypsophia vaccaria, Orobanche cernua, Ammni visnaga, Cichorium intybus, L Galium tricornutum</i>
ES TD1	<i>Astragalus hamosus, Calendula arvensis, Diplotaxis eruroides, Diplotaxis virgata, Erodium malacoides, Filago lutescens, Bromus rubens, Crepis vesicaria, Hordeum marinum, Leontodon longistrostris, Lolium rigidum, Medicago polymorpha, Silene colorata, Capsella bursapastoris, Medicago campestre, Torilis nodosa, Sinapis alba, Glebionis segetum, Bromus madritensis, Trigonella mospeliaca, Anacyclus clavatus, Bromus hordeaceus, Althaea hirsuta, Medicago minima, Papaver roeas, Plantago lagopus, Brachypodium distachyon, Roemeria argemone, Scorzonera lacianata</i>
ES TD5	<i>Aegilops geniculata, Anacyclus clavatus, Avena sterilis, Bromus rubens, Hordeum marinum, Lolium rigidum, Medicago minima, Medicago polymorpha, Hirschfeldia incana, Leontodon longistrostris, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus madritensis, Belardia trixago, Papaver rhoeas, Capsella bursapastoris, Sonchus oleraceus, Cicer arietinum</i>
ES TD7	<i>Euphorbia exigua, Medicago minima, Bromus rubens, Erodium malacoides, Lolium rigidum, Hordeum marinum, Althaea hirsuta, Papaver rhoeas, Vicia lutea, Diplotaxis virgata, Euphorbia peplus, Medicago polymorpha, Torilis nodosa, Lamium amplexicaule, Scorpiurus mericatus, Capsella bursapastoris, Carduus nigrescens,</i>

	<i>Crepis vesicaria, Sonchus oleraceus, Tragopogon angustifolius, Urospermum picroides, Crepis foetida, Galium aparine, Lactuca serraiola, Lysimachia foemina, Hirschfeldia incana, Bromus madritensis, Convolvulus arvensis</i>
ES TD9	<i>Astragalus hamosus, Calendula arvensis, Capsella bursapastoris, Erodium malacoides, Galium aparine, Lolium rigidum, Lysimachia foemina, Althaea hirsuta, Medicago polymorpha, Poa annua, Sonchus oleraceus, Anacyclus clavatus, Bromus rubens, Hordeum marinum, Medicago orbicularis, Hirschfeldia incana, Torilis nodosa, Diplotaxis virgata, Senecio vulgaris, Erodium moschatum, Leontodon longistrostris, Lamium amplexicaule, Geranium rotundifolium, Plantago lagopus, Bromus hordeaceus, Crepis vesicaria, Convolvulus arvensis, Diplotaxis muralis, Scorpiurus mericatus, Cynodon dactylon</i>
ES TD15	<i>Erodium malacoides, Erodium moschatum, Bupleurum lancifolium, Galium aparine, Geranium rotundifolium, Medicago orbicularis, Sinapis alba, Anacyclus clavatus, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus rubens, Calendula arvensis, Convolvulus arvensis, Hordeum marinum, Lysimachia foemina, Pallenis spinosa, Capsella bursapastoris, Veronica polita, Medicago polymorpha, Torilis nodosa, Diplotaxis virgata, Lolium rigidum, Malva hispanica, Crepis vesicaria, Papaver rhoeas, Sonchus oleraceus, Urtica urens, Lamium amplexicaule</i>
IT TD16	<i>Avena fatua, Bromus sterilis, Calendula arvensis, Cerinthe minor L. subsp. Auriculata, Chamaemelum fuscatum, Convolvulus tricolor, Diplotaxis eruroides ssp. eruroides, Galacties tomentosus, Lulium multiflorum, Lysimachia arvensis, Malva multiflora, Medicago ciliaris, Medicago polymorpha, Picris hieracioides, Ridolfia segetum, Sonchus asper, Beta vulgaris L. ssp. maritima, Brassica nigra, Phalaris paradoxa, Cynodon dactylon</i>
IT TD20	<i>Avena fatua, Borago officinalis, Diplotaxis eruroides ssp. eruroides, Euphorbia helioscopia, Galacties tomentosus, Malva multiflora, Medicago polymorpha, Mercurialis annua, Oxalis pes-caprae, Sonchus asper, Stellaria neglecta spp. cupaniana, Vicia sativa, Chenopodium murale, Chrysanthemum coronarium, Erodium moschatum, Hordeum murinum, Senecio vulgaris, Urospermum picroides</i>
IT TD21	<i>Asparagus acutifolius, Avena barbata, Bituminaria bituminosa, Brachypodium sylvaticum, Bromus arvensis, Campanula rapunculus, Chenopodium berlandieri, Crepis capillaris, Medicago orbicularis, Medicago polymorpha, Nigella damascena, Ornithogalum umbellatum, Sanguisorba minor, Sonchus asper, Veronica ITA sp, Allium neapolitanum, Ampelodesmos mauritanicus, Anacamptis pyramidalis, Anthyllis vulneraria, Asphodelus ramosus, Briza maxima, Cirsium vulgare, Seseli tortuosum, Silybum marianum, Smilax aspera, Urospermum dalechampii, Centaurium erythraea, Convolvulus cantabrica, Ornithogalum narbonense, Sonchus tenerimus, Erigeron sumatrensis, Linum trigynum, Malope malacoides, Muscari neglectum, Rubia peregrina, Salvia verbenaca, Scabiosa atropurpurea, Tordylium apulum, Asphodelus macrocarpus, Silene latifolia, Sonchus oleraceus, Pallenis spinosa, Crepis bursifolia, Euphorbia characias, Lotus ornithopodioides, Stellaria media, Trifolium stellatum, Carduus pycnocephalus, Lathyrus sylvestris, Melica ciliata, Trachynia distachya, Asparagus tenuifolius, Euphorbia spinosa, Picris hieracioides, Serapias parviflora, Clinopodium nepeta nepeta, Dactylis glomerata, Daucus carota, Hypericum perforatum</i>
GR TD35	<i>Anthemis chia, Avena sativa, Cistus creticus, Papaver rhoeas, Thymbra capitata</i>
GR TD36	<i>Anthemis chia, Avena sativa, Papaver rhoeas</i>
GR TD37	<i>Anthemis chia, Avena sativa, Crepis commutata, Trifolium stellatum</i>
PT TD41	<i>Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus rubens, Crepis vesicaria, Coleostephus myconis, Echium creticum, Lactuca viminea, Galium aparine, Gaudinia fragilis, Hedypnois rhagadioloides, Hypochaeris glabra, Anthemis arvensis, Plantago coronopus, Sanguisorba minor, Silene gallica, Trifolium tomentosum, Lathyrus angulatus, Avena sterilis, Leontodon longistrostris, Sherardia arvensis, Biserrula pelecinus, Bromus tectorum, Dactylis glomerata, Erodium moschatum, Lotus conimbricensis, Parentucellia latifolia, Convolvulus arvensis, Diplotaxis virgata, Aira caryophyllea,</i>

	<i>Trifolium campestre, Veronica polita, Allium PT, Bromus diandrus, Calendula arvensis, Eruca sativa, Hordeum marinum, Lolium rigidum</i>
MR TD24	<i>Medicago polymorpha, Silybum marianum, Calendula stellata, Torilis nodosa, Launaea nudicaulis, Hypochaeris glabra, Trifolium tomentosum, Glebionis coronaria, Sigesbeckia orientalis, Helminthotheca echioides</i>
MR TD26	<i>Oxalis per-caprae, Caléndula stellata, Hordeum marinum, Glebionis coronaria, Dactylis glomerata, Echium plantagineum, Malva parviflora, Launaea nudicaulis, Polentilla recta</i>
MR-TD27	<i>Medicago polymorpha, Vicia benghalensis, Atriplex semibaccata, Solanum elaeagnifolium, Caléndula stellata, Papaver rhoeas, Cynodon dactylon, Galium tricornutum, Vicia sativa</i>
MR-TD28	<i>Papaver rhoeas, Gypsophia vaccaria, Caléndula stellata, Medicago polymorpha, Chrysanthemum cornarium, Brassica nigra, Malva parviflora, Chenopodium álbum, Plantago afra</i>
MR-TD29	<i>Malva parviflora, Solanum elaeagnifolium, Hordeum marinum, Oxalis per-caprae, Cynodon dactylon, Launaea nudicaulis, Anagallis foemina, Sinapis arvensis, Galium tricornutum</i>

Percentage of coverage

Figure 7. Boxplot of percentage of soil coverage differentiating by country and management system.

The results show that, in Greece, Italy, Morocco, and Spain, organic orchards consistently exhibit higher ground cover compared to orchards under other management systems. In contrast, the lowest ground cover values were observed in high-density orchards, suggesting that orchard structure and management practices both play a role in shaping vegetation cover. Higher ground cover in organic orchards also helps prevent problems associated with bare soil, such as erosion, nutrient loss, and reduced soil moisture retention.

Hills numbers.

Figure 8. Hill numbers of groundcovers differentiating by management.

Figure 9. Hill numbers of groundcovers differentiating by management.

Regarding species richness, we found that organically managed orchards (Fig. 8) consistently support higher biodiversity compared to other management systems, with the difference being particularly pronounced when compared to high-density orchards. Examining biodiversity at the country level, Italy exhibited the highest species richness among the studied countries (Fig. 9). This pattern may be influenced by the presence of two distinct sampling regions (two different NUTS areas) in Italy—one continental and one on an island—which, when combined, result in higher overall species richness. In contrast, Spain has only a single NUTS region sampled, yet still demonstrates relatively high species richness. A different pattern is observed in Portugal, where two NUTS regions were sampled; however, the Alentejo region consists exclusively of high-density orchards with lower species richness, which explains why the elevated biodiversity observed in Italy is not reflected there.

For Morocco, the sites were not included in the hills number analysis because

only ground cover data and a species list were available, without the detailed abundance or frequency information required for this metric.

4.2. Seed-bank.

Those species that could not be identified to the species level are expressed up to the taxon that could be determined, accompanied by the region in which they were found.

Table 4. Herbaceous species of seed bank by orchard.

Orchard No	Species
ES-TD1	<i>Astragalus hamosus</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Bromus tectorum</i> , <i>Erigeron spainspp</i> , <i>Lamarckia aurea</i> , <i>Lepidium incanum</i> , <i>Muscari neglectum</i> , <i>Torilis nodosa</i>
ES-HD2	<i>Galium murale</i>
ES-HD3	<i>Arenaria spp</i> , <i>Centaurea melitensis</i> , <i>Euphorbia prostata</i> , <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Galium murale</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Spinacia oleracea</i>
ES-ORG4	<i>Aegilops geniculata</i> , <i>Astragalus hamosus</i> , <i>Avena spp</i> , <i>Brachypodium spainspp</i> , <i>Bromus hordeaceus</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Bromus tectorum</i> , <i>Calendula arvensis</i> , <i>Carduus tenuiflorus</i> , <i>Crepis mollis</i> , <i>Euphorbia exigua</i> , <i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i> , <i>Geranium spainspp</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Medicago polymorpha</i> , <i>Plantago spainspp</i> , <i>Stipa capensis</i> , <i>Rubiacea spainspp</i> , <i>Scandix pecten</i>
ES-TD5	<i>Bromus hordeaceus</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Hordeum murinum</i> , <i>Medicago polymorpha</i> , <i>Secale cereale</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Spergularia arvensis</i>
ES-ORG6	<i>Brachypodium distachyon</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Bromus secalinus</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Urospermum picroides</i>
ES-TD7	<i>Bromus madritensis</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Hordeum murinum</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Lolium rigidum</i> , <i>Medicago orbicularis</i> , <i>Poacea spainspp1</i> , <i>Scorpiurus muricatus</i> , <i>Taraxacum obovatum</i>
ES-HD8	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Crepis spainspp2</i> , <i>Erodium moschatum</i> , <i>Geranium pusillum</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Stellaria media</i> , <i>Urtica urens</i> , <i>Veronica arvensis</i>
ES-TD9	<i>Bromus hordeaceus</i> , <i>Crepis spainspp1</i> , <i>Cyperus spainspp</i> , <i>Galium spainspp</i> , <i>Hirschfeldia incana</i> , <i>Hordeum murinum</i> , <i>Malva parviflora</i> , <i>Medicago orbicularis</i> , <i>Medicago polymorpha</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Scorpiurus muricatus</i> , <i>Senecio vulgaris</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Stellaria media</i> , <i>Torilis nodosa</i>
ES-ORG11	<i>Anacyclus clavatus</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Calendula arvensis</i> , <i>Crepis spainspp2</i> , <i>Diploaxis virgata</i> , <i>Lamium amplexicaule</i> , <i>Lysimachia spainspp</i> , <i>Malva spainspp</i> , <i>Muscari neglectum</i> , <i>Poa palustris</i> , <i>Poa spainspp</i> , <i>Poacea spainspp2</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Stachys arvensis</i> , <i>Torilis nodosa</i> , <i>Urospermum picroides</i>
ES-ORG12	<i>Anacyclus clavatus</i> , <i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Hordeum murinum</i> , <i>Poacea spainspp3</i> , <i>Poacea spainspp4</i> , <i>Primulacea spainspp2</i> , <i>Scorpiurus muricatus</i> , <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> , <i>Stellaria media</i>
ES-ORG13	<i>Brachypodium spainspp</i> , <i>Brassicacea spainspp</i> , <i>Galium parisiense</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Lysimachia arvensis</i> , <i>Malva neglecta</i> , <i>Medicago polymorpha</i> , <i>Torilis nodosa</i>
ES-ORG14	<i>Anacyclus clavatus</i> , <i>Centaurea melitensis</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Muscari neglectum</i> , <i>Plantago lanceolata</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Rostraria cristata</i> , <i>Scorpiurus muricatus</i> , <i>Sisymbrium loeselii</i>
ES-TD15	<i>Bromus rubens</i> , <i>Capsella spainspp</i> , <i>Convolvulus spainspp</i> , <i>Galium spainspp</i> , <i>Geranium molle</i> , <i>Lamium amplexicaule</i> , <i>Leontodon longirostris</i> , <i>Malva parviflora</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Poacea spainspp5</i>

IT-TD16	<i>Calendula arvensis, Oxalis opes-caprea, Poacea italyspp, Veronica italyspp</i>
IT-ORG17	<i>Medicago italyspp, Oxalis opes-caprea</i>
IT-ORG18	<i>Poacea italyspp1, Poacea italyspp2, Sonchus italyspp, Stellaria media</i>
IT-ORG19	<i>Apiacea italyspp, Chenopodium vulvaria, Poacea italyspp2, Poacea italyspp3, Stellaria media</i>
IT-TD20	<i>Calendula arvensis, Chenopodium murale, Crepis italyspp, Digitaria sanguinalis, Portulaca oleraceae, Setaria adherens, Solanum italyspp, Stellaria media, Urtica italyspp</i>
IT-TD21	<i>Euphorbia italyspp, Lysimachia arvensis, Mercurialis annua, Sonchus italyspp</i>
ES-HD22	<i>Bromus madritensis, Bromus secalinus, Poacea spainspp2, Poacea spainspp6, Rostraria cristata, Rubiaceae spainspp, Sisymbrium spainspp</i>
MR-ORG23	<i>Apiacea moroccospp, Tyrimmus leucographus, Veronica moroccospp</i>
MR-TD24	<i>Poacea moroccospp1</i>
MR-HD25	<i>Medicago moroccospp, Sonchus moroccospp</i>
MR-TD26	<i>Chenopodium album, Heliotropium europaeum</i>
MR-TD27	<i>Chenopodium moroccospp, Chenopodium murale, Poacea moroccospp2, Stellaria media, Tyrimmus leucographus, Veronica moroccospp</i>
MR-HD28	<i>Chenopodium murale</i>
MR-TD29	<i>Calendula arvensis, Poa moroccospp</i>
GR-TD30	<i>Amarylliferae greecespp, Chenopodium greecespp, Dichondra greecespp, Mercurialis annua, Poa annua, Stellaria media, Urtica urens</i>
GR-TD31	<i>Geranium molle, Heliotropium hirsutissimum, Lolium perenne</i>
GR-ORG32	<i>Brachypodium greecespp, Calendula arvensis, Cotula greecespp, Scorpiurus muricatus, Theligonum cynocrambre L</i>
GR-ORG33	<i>Amarylliferae greecespp, Avena spp, Brachypodium distachyon, Bromus scoparius, Capsicum annuum, Erodium malacoides, Lolium perenne, Lysimachia arvensis, Mercurialis annua, Oloptum miliaceum, Rhagadiolus edulis, Scandix pecten-veneris, Sonchus greecespp, Torilis nodosa, Veronica greecespp1</i>
GR-ORG34	<i>Amarylliferae greecespp, Asteraceae greecespp4, Brassicaceae greecespp2, Chenopodium album, Medicago orbicularis, Mercurialis annua, Veronica cymbalaria</i>
GR-TD35	<i>Apiacea greecespp2, Asteraceae greecespp3, Avena greecespp, Brassicaceae greecespp2, Caryophyllaceae greecespp2, Crepis foetida, Medicago greecespp1, Muscari greecespp, Poacea greecespp1, Poacea greecespp2, Poacea greecespp3, Poacea greecespp4, Scorpiurus greecespp, Stellaria media</i>
GR-TD36	<i>Brachypodium greecespp, Chamaemelum nobile, Crepis greecespp, Euphorbia greecespp, Medicago greecespp2, Poacea greecespp2, Poacea greecespp3, Poacea greecespp5, Poaceae greecespp1, Poaceae greecespp5, Scorpiurus greecespp, Senecio vulgaris, Sonchus greecespp, Stellaria media Caryophyllaceae greecespp3, Euphorbia helioscopia, Galium greecespp, Lysimachia arvensis, Medicago greecespp1, Poacea greecespp2, Poaceae greecespp3, Poaceae greecespp5, Sonchus greecespp, Stellaria media, Veronica greecespp2</i>
GR-TD37	<i>Caryophyllaceae greecespp3, Euphorbia helioscopia, Galium greecespp, Lysimachia arvensis, Medicago greecespp1, Poacea greecespp2, Poaceae greecespp3, Poaceae greecespp5, Sonchus greecespp, Stellaria media, Veronica greecespp2</i>
GR-ORG38	<i>Apiacea greecespp1, Avena greecespp, Euphorbia helioscopia, Euphorbia peplus, Lysimachia linum-stellatum, Medicago greecespp2, Poaceae greecespp2, Poaceae</i>

	<i>grecespp3, Poaceae grecespp6, Rosaceae grecespp, Sonchus grecespp, Veronica grecespp1</i>
GR-ORG39	<i>Apiacea grecespp1, Avena barbata, Boraginacea grecespp2, Caryophyllacea grecespp1, Euphorbia peplus, Medicago grecespp3, Poaceae grecespp2, Poaceae grecespp3, Sonchus pulcra, Stellaria media, Trifolium grecespp, Veronica grecespp3</i>
ES-HD40	<i>Avena spainspp, Bromus hordeaceus, Bromus rubens, Erodium malacoides, Galium spainspp, Lysimachia arvensis, Poa annua, Scorpiurus muricatus, Solanum villosum, Sysimbrium spp</i>
PR-TD41	<i>Apiacea portugalspp, Coleostephus myconis, Gaudinia fragilis, Muscari neglectum, Pallenis spinosa, Poacea portugalspp, Reseda luteola, Senecio vulgaris, Solanum nigrum, Sonchus oleraceus</i>
PT-ORG42	<i>Cerastium glomeratum, Chamaemelum nobile, Chenopodium album, Eruca vesicaria, Lepidium sativum, Poa portugalspp, Portulaca oleracea, Sonchus portugalspp</i>
GR-TD44	<i>Asteracea grecespp2, Brassicacea grecespp1, Brassicacea grecespp3, Echium asperrimum, Lolium rigidum, Lysimachia arvensis, Medicago grecespp2, Oxalis pes-caprae</i>
GR-ORG45	<i>Andrachne telephioides, Echium grecespp, Fabacea grecespp1, Fabacea grecespp2, Medicago orbicularis, Oloptum miliaceum, Oxalis pes-caprae, Urospermum picroides</i>
GR-TD46	<i>Convolvulus grecespp, Daucus grecespp, Lysimachia arvensis, Lythrum hyssopifolia, Mercurialis annua, Panicum miliaceum, Setaria verticillata</i>
GR-ORG47	<i>Brassicacea grecespp1, Oxalis pes-caprae, Solanum nigrum</i>
IT-ORG49	<i>Asteracea italyspp2, Chenopodium vulvaria, Convolvulus italyspp, Geranium italyspp, Poacea italyspp5, Scorpiurus spp</i>
IT-TD50	<i>Asteracea italyspp1, Poacea italyspp4</i>
PT-HD51	<i>Chenopodium album, Chenopodium vulvaria, Convolvulus portugalspp, Cyperacea portugalspp, Muscaris neglectum</i>
PT-HD52	<i>Bromus rubens, Echium portugalspp, Filago pyramidata, Muscari neglectum</i>
PT-HD53	<i>Cynodon dactylon, Raphanus raphanistrum</i>

Hills numbers.

Figure 10. Photographs of the seedling identification phase.

We calculated Hill numbers to assess diversity both globally among different management types and spatially at the NUT2 level. The Hill numbers include q_0 , which represents species richness (the total number of species); q_1 , which corresponds to the exponential of Shannon entropy and gives more weight to common species; and q_2 , which is the inverse of Simpson's index and emphasizes dominant species. As key results, we found a lower number of

species in high-density orchards compared to the other management types, with special attention to the two estates located in Alentejo, as both are high-density systems.

Figure 11. Boxplots showing diversity indices (Hill numbers) by management type. ANOVA tests were performed to assess differences among management systems.

When calculating the Hill numbers for each orchard, we found that organic farms showed higher diversity values, which were statistically significant for q_0 and marginally significant for q_1 . According to the post hoc analysis, these significant differences were only observed when comparing organic and high-density orchards, while no significant differences were detected in pairs involving conventional management. No significant differences were found for

q_2 , which indicates that the dominance structure of species (i.e., how evenly dominant species are distributed) is similar across management types. In other words, although the number and relative abundance of species vary, the most dominant species tend to contribute similarly to community composition in all management systems.

Figure 12. Boxplots showing diversity indices (Hill numbers) by countries. ANOVA tests were performed to assess differences among countries.

When comparing countries, Spanish orchards showed the highest median values for q_0 (species richness), and were significantly different only from orchards in Morocco and Italy. In contrast, Greek orchards presented the highest values for q_1 and q_2 , indicating greater diversity when accounting for species abundances, and showed significant differences mainly when compared with Moroccan orchards, which displayed the lowest Hill numbers.

These patterns suggest different ecological dynamics behind the diversity structure of each region. The higher q_0 values in Spain indicate that more species are present overall, likely influenced by a combination of climatic heterogeneity, landscape complexity, and management practices that favor the presence of a larger seed pool. Meanwhile, the greater q_1 and q_2 values detected in Greece reveal not only the presence of many species, but also a more even distribution among them - meaning there are fewer highly dominant species. This implies a more functionally balanced community, which may enhance ecosystem resilience and stability. In contrast, lower diversity values in Moroccan orchards indicate a stronger dominance of a few species and/or a reduced availability of environmental conditions that support diverse plant communities.

Biodiversity drivers.

Figure 13. Pearson's correlations between Hill's numbers and orchards context variables.

Pearson correlations showed that Hill numbers were positively associated with plantation age, latitude, slope, and the landscape ENN index, and negatively associated with plantation density and mean annual temperature. This indicates that older, less dense orchards, located at higher latitudes, on steeper slopes, or in more spatially isolated landscapes tend to support more species and more even communities. These results highlight the importance of both local orchard characteristics and landscape context in maintaining biodiversity, suggesting that management strategies preserving older, less dense trees and heterogeneous landscapes can enhance species richness and community

balance.

Figure 14. Pearson's correlations between Hill's numbers and soil drivers.

Hill numbers were positively correlated with soil organic matter, organic carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and silt content, while they were negatively associated with bulk density. This suggests that fertile, well-structured soils with balanced texture promote higher species richness and more even communities, likely by providing better resources and conditions for seed germination and seedling establishment. In contrast, compacted soils with high bulk density may limit root growth and reduce habitat heterogeneity, thereby constraining biodiversity.

Figure 15. Pearson's correlations between Hill's numbers and soil drivers.

When performing a PCA including orchard context, soil variables, and biodiversity indices, we found that PC1 primarily reflects soil texture, while PC2 represents orchard context. Positive values along PC2 correspond to higher longitude, plantation age, organic carbon, and nitrogen, and align with higher

Hill numbers. In contrast, negative values in both dimensions (lower-left quadrant) are associated with high tree density, larger orchard size, higher irrigation levels, and greater bulk density. This pattern suggests that both soil properties and orchard management jointly structure biodiversity, with more fertile, older, and less dense orchards supporting richer and more even communities.

6. Conclusions

Overall, the results indicate that organic orchards consistently exhibited both higher species richness and greater herbaceous ground cover, whereas high-density orchards showed lower values for these metrics. The patterns observed for herbaceous cover closely mirrored those found in the seed bank, suggesting a strong relationship between aboveground vegetation and the potential seed reservoir. At the same time, seed bank biodiversity was strongly influenced by management type, soil conditions, and orchard context: high-density systems consistently showed lower species richness, while organic orchards displayed higher diversity values, particularly for richness (q_0) and abundance-weighted diversity (q_1). This indicates that less intensive agricultural practices—characterized by lower planting density and greater soil and habitat heterogeneity—promote more diverse and balanced plant communities. The similarity in q_2 values across management types, however, suggests that despite differences in species number and abundance, the dominance structure remains relatively stable.

At the regional scale, differences among countries reflect the combined effects of climatic, topographic, and management factors on community structure. Higher species richness and cover in Spain and Greece contrast with lower diversity in Morocco, where only ground cover and species presence data were available, preventing inclusion in the hills number analysis. Correlations with environmental and soil variables further indicate that diversity tends to increase in older, less dense orchards with fertile, well-structured soils and in more spatially complex or isolated landscapes. Altogether, these findings highlight the importance of management practices that maintain structural heterogeneity, soil quality, and lower intensity as key strategies to conserve and enhance biodiversity in Mediterranean agroecosystems.